

(MINI REVIEW)

Elimination of the new coronavirus and prevention of the second wave of infection

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Abstract

Every virus is a parasite. They cannot exist alone, they depend on their wearer. This is the basic condition of its existence. What living cell carries viruses? Based on work with bovine leukosis virus (BLV) and HIV, we have found that bacteria can host the virus. We tested this assumption and confirmed the results. Based on these results and indications, we have come to the conclusion that viruses, including coronavirus, are transmitted by bacteria or yeast. By destroying the bacteria carrying the viruses, the virus ceases to exist.

Keywords: BLV; HIV; Bacteria; Yeasts; Second wave

1. Introduction

The coronavirus is far from over. Some countries are still facing epidemics, but even those currently controlling the virus fear a "second wave". However, the second wave could theoretically be stronger than the first. There is no formal definition for the second wave yet. The views of the expert are unclear and vague. The general opinion is that the definition of the second wave cannot be expressed correctly. This statement does not stand up, because there are certain laws in biology and this phenomenon needs to be explained.

Every virus is a parasite. They cannot exist alone, they depend on their wearer. This is the basic condition of its existence. Very little is still known about how they can jump from one species to another and finally spread to humans. After all, a parasite must have its host, a living cell. It is generally claimed that a virus can exist for as little as 2-5 seconds during which it spreads to another species. But this goes against the basic dogma that a virus cannot exist without a living cell. Naturally, tracking these viral journeys is not easy and has not been fully researched. However, this is a key issue, the solution of which can lead to a fundamental reversal in how we view viruses.

What living cell carries viruses? Based on work with bovine leukosis virus (BLV) in the stables, we monitored the course of infection in healthy animals and concluded that a bacterial cell can be the host of the virus. We tested this assumption and confirmed the results. This idea was then tested on the HIV model in the laboratory of Prof. Flossie Wong-Staal, (UCSD). Even with this virus, we have been able to prove that its host may be bacteria. Evidence was confirmed at the DNA level by hybridization and PCR using commercial, diagnostic primers and consequent sequencing. At the protein level, HIV-like proteins were confirmed by Western blotting using commercial monoclonal antibodies against HIV antigens (1-10). In the swabs of HIV-positive children from Cambodia and Kenya, HIV was found in commensal bacteria, but it is also often found in the yeast *Candida albicans* (4 -7). Based on these results, it was concluded that many, if not all viruses can be transmitted by bacteria, or by yeast. If all, the coronavirus.

A virus, just like a parasite, is not a full-fledged biological form and thus hard to fight. Its main weakness is that it is hosted by bacteria or yeast. Bacteria are a complete biological form and they can be eliminated. By destroying bacteria carrying a virus, the virus ceases to exist. Thus, many viral infections can be stopped. It should be ascertained whether

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the current pandemic has been caused by bacteria or coronavirus-containing yeast. It is likely that such coronavirus is transmitted to humans and travels further to the recipient cells of the respiratory and intestinal tract. Upon contact of the viral tentacles with the ACE2 receptor, the virus is released and penetrates the recipient cell of the respiratory tract and the process of tissue destruction begins.

Thus, after overcoming the infection, eliminating the virus in the lung cells, the virus-containing bacteria are still present in the respiratory and intestinal tracts and under optimal conditions, they multiply. Consequently penetrate the body through the cardiovascular system and attack the recipient's cells. Thus, individuals after infection can infect other individuals by secreting coronavirus-containing bacteria from the mouth, nose, but also from the rectum in the stool. This reversal, called the second wave of infection, can be prevented by applying appropriate antibiotics, which eliminate coronavirus-containing bacteria in the intestinal and respiratory tracts.

To verify this conception, a throat swab needs to be collected from an infected person. The swab is transferred directly applied to agar, blood agar, or other richer growth medium and incubated overnight at 37 °C. Individual grown bacterial colonies will be determined by RT PCR for coronavirus. Subsequently, it will be analyzed to which antibiotics the bacteria containing the coronavirus are fully sensitive. The optimal antibiotic is administered to the patient. Under normal circumstances, it is expected that the results may be known within 10 days. Patients should be given probiotics and prebiotics after the antibiotic treatment. The proposed approach of identification and treatment of coronavirus infections is very rapid. The most important aspect is starting the treatment at the earliest opportunity. By finding a suitable antibiotic to kill the virus-containing host cells, we can immediately intervene straight at the beginning of the disease process.

2. Conclusion

Based on work with the bovine leukosis virus (BLV) and HIV, we found that the virus can be hosted by bacteria or even yeast. By eliminating these bacteria, the virus loses its host and dies. Applying this idea to the coronavirus can stop it from spreading.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The author declares that there is no conflict of interest.

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Author's short biography

Vladimir Zajac has completed his PhD. in 1982 at the Cancer Research Institute of Slovak Academy of Sciences in Bratislava (Slovakia), where he worked as the Head of Department of Cancer Genetics from 1996 to 2010. He joined the Medical Faculty of the Comenius University as Associate Professor of Genetics in 2007. He has published 74 papers mostly in reputed journals and he was editor of the book “Bacteria, viruses and parasites in AIDS process” (In Tech, 2011).